

**ILMIY VA
INNOVATSION
TERAPIYA**

**SCIENTIFIC >>> >>>
AND INNOVATIVE
THERAPY**

2025, № 2 (Май)

МИНИСТЕРСТВО ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ
РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН

**SCIENTIFIC AND INNOVATIVE
THERAPY**

**ИЛМИЙ ВА ИННОВАЦИОН
ТЕРАПИЯ**

**НАУЧНАЯ И ИННОВАЦИОННАЯ
ТЕРАПИЯ**

Научный журнал по научной и инновационной терапии
основано в 2022 году

Бухарским государственным медицинским институтом
имени Абу Али ибн Сино
выходит один раз в 2 месяца

Главный редактор – Ш.Ж. ТЕШАЕВ

Редакционная коллегия:

*Н.Ш. Ахмедова (зам. главного редактора),
Ш.А. Наимова (ответственный секретарь),
Г.Ж. Жарилкасинова, Н.А. Нуралиев, К.Ж. Болтаев,
Ф.Э. Нурбаев, С.М. Бахрамов, А.Г. Гадаев,
А.Ш. Иноятов, Р.Б. Абдуллаев*

*Учредитель Бухарский государственный
медицинский институт имени Абу Али ибн Сино*

ISSN
2181-418X

2025, № 2 (Май)

Адрес редакции:

Республика Узбекистан, 200100,
г. Бухара, ул. А. Гиждувани, 23.

Телефон:

(99865) 223-00-50

Факс

(99866) 223-00-50

Сайт

<https://ivit.uz/>

e-mail

shnaimova5@gmail.com

О журнале

Журнал зарегистрирован
в Управлении печати и информации
Бухарской области
№ 1640 от 28.05.2022 г.

Подписано в печать 20.11.2023.

Формат 60×84 1/8

Усл. П.л. 41,39

Заказ 104

Тираж 50 экз.

Отпечатано в типографии Шарк

140151, г. Бухары,

ул. Амира Темура, 18

Редакционный совет:

Anand Ahuja	(Индия)
Nordin Simbak	(Малайзия)
Tetsuo Sasano	(Япония)
Ali O'zdemir	(Туркия)
Есяян А.М.	(Россия)
Арипова Т.У.	(Узбекистан)
Ахмедов Р.М.	(Узбекистан)
Амонов М.К.	(Узбекистан)
Бадритдинова М.Н.	(Узбекистан)
Бобоев К.Т.	(Узбекистан)
Давлатов С.С.	(Узбекистан)
Дустова Н.К.	(Узбекистан)
Курманова Г.М.	(Казахстан)
Қаюмов А.А.	(Узбекистан)
Мавлянов З.И.	(Узбекистан)
Набиева Д.А.	(Узбекистан)
Неъматов Ж.М.	(Узбекистан)
Пўлатов С.С.	(Узбекистан)
Рахматова Д.И.	(Узбекистан)
Саноева М.Ж.	(Узбекистан)
Сулаймонова Г.Т.	(Узбекистан)
Тўракулов Р.И.	(Узбекистан)
Шодиқулова Г.З.	(Узбекистан)
Эгамова С.Қ.	(Узбекистан)
Юлдашева Д.Х.	(Узбекистан)
Убайдуллаева З.И.	(Узбекистан)
Нуруллоев С.О.	(Узбекистан)

INFLUENCE OF FIBROBLAST GROWTH FACTOR 23 ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF NEPHROPATHY IN CHRONIC HEART FAILURE

Djurayeva Nozima Orifovna

Bukhara State Medical Institute, Bukhara, Uzbekistan

Senior lecturer of the Department of retraining and advanced training of family physicians

<https://orsid.org/0009-0008-4955-5054>

E-mail: djurayeva.nozima@bsmi.uz

Abstract Fibroblast growth factor 23 (FGF23) is a key regulator of phosphate homeostasis that plays an important role in the pathophysiology of chronic heart failure (CHF) and chronic kidney disease (CKD). In recent years, its participation in the development of nephropathy on the background of CHF has been actively studied. The aim of this review article is to analyse the current data on the role of FGF23 in the progression of nephropathy in CHF, mechanisms of action, clinical relationships and prospects for therapeutic action.

Keywords: Fibroblast Growth Factor 23, chronic heart failure, chronic kidney disease, Klotho protein

ФИБРОБЛАСТ ЎСИШ ОМИЛИ-23НИНГ СУРУНКАЛИ ЮРАК ЕТИШМОВЧИЛИГИДА НЕФРОПАТИЯ РИВОЖЛАНИШИГА ТАЪСИРИ

Джураева Нозима Орифовна

Бухоро Давлат Тиббиёт Институти, Бухоро, Ўзбекистон

Оилавий шифокорларни қайта тайёрлаш ва малакасини ошириш кафедраси катта ўқитувчиси

<https://orsid.org/0009-0008-4955-5054>

E-mail: djurayeva.nozima@bsmi.uz

Аннотация Сурункали юрак етишмовчилиги ва сурункали буйрак касаллиги патофизиологиясида муҳим ўрин тутувчи фосфат гемостазинининг асосий бошқарувчи омили бу фибробласт ўсиш омили 23 (FGF 23) ҳисобланади. Сўнгги йилларда унинг сурункали юрак етишмовчилиги фонида нефропатия ривожланишидаги иштироки фаол ўрганилмоқда. Ушбу шарҳловчи мақоланинг мақсади FGF 23 нинг сурункали юрак етишмовчилигидаги нефропатиянинг ривожланишидаги роли, таъсир механизмлари, клиник боғлиқлиги ва терапевтик таъсир истиқболлари ҳақидаги жорий маълумотларни таҳлил қилишдир.

Калит сўзлар: фибробласт ўсиш омили 23, сурункали юрак етишмовчилиги, сурункали буйрак касаллиги, Клото оксиди

ВЛИЯНИЕ ФАКТОР РОСТА ФИБРОБЛАСТОВ 23 НА РАЗВИТИЕ НЕФРОПАТИИ ПРИ ХРОНИЧЕСКОЙ СЕРДЕЧНОЙ НЕДОСТАТОЧНОСТИ

Джураева Нозима Орифовна

Бухарский государственный медицинский институт, Бухара, Узбекистан

Старший преподаватель кафедры переподготовки и повышения квалификации семейных врачей

<https://orsid.org/0009-0008-4955-5054>

E-mail: djurayeva.nozima@bsmi.uz

Аннотация Фактор роста фибробластов 23 (FGF23) представляет собой ключевой регулятор фосфатного гомеостаза, играющий важную роль в патофизиологии хронической сердечной недостаточности (ХСН) и хронической болезни почек (ХБП). В последние годы активно изучается его участие в развитии нефропатии на фоне ХСН. Целью настоящей обзорной статьи является анализ современных данных о роли FGF23 в прогрессировании нефропатии при ХСН, механизмах действия, клинических взаимосвязях и перспективах терапевтического воздействия.

Ключевые слова: Фактор роста фибробластов 23, хронической сердечной недостаточности, хронической болезни почек, белок Клото

Cardiovascular disease (CVD) is a prominent feature in children with chronic kidney disease (CKD), which increases the risk of all-cause mortality and cardiovascular disease in these patients. A bone-derived phosphaturic hormone, fibroblast growth factor (FGF) 23, increases progressively with worsening renal function to maintain phosphate homeostasis. In patients with renal failure requiring dialysis, its levels increase 1000-fold. FGF23 is associated with the development of left ventricular hypertrophy (LVH) and is thus a risk factor for cardiovascular disease in CKD. FGF23 has been experimentally demonstrated to directly induce hypertrophic growth of cardiomyocytes in vitro and GLJ in vivo. In addition, clinical studies of adult CKD have revealed cardiotoxicity associated with FGF23 [1].

Chronic heart failure (CHF) is a clinical syndrome characterised by reduced pumping function of the heart, resulting in systemic hypoperfusion and congestion. The relationship between the heart and kidneys has long been known, and the term 'cardio-renal syndrome' reflects the complex interaction between these organs. In recent years, special attention has been paid to the role of FGF23, a hormone produced by osteocytes, in the pathogenesis of this pathology [1].

FGF23 (fibroblast growth factor 23) was discovered as a key regulator of phosphate metabolism and vitamin D metabolism. It is synthesised predominantly in

bone tissue and acts on the kidneys by reducing phosphate reabsorption and inhibiting 1-alpha-hydroxylase activity, thereby reducing calcitriol production. The biological activity of FGF23 requires the cofactor Klotho, which is expressed in kidneys and other tissues [2].

FGF23 was first identified in 2000 during studies aimed at elucidating the causes of rare inherited diseases such as hypophosphatemic rickets. Since then, attention to FGF23 has increased significantly, especially in the context of its role in mineral metabolism disorders, cardiovascular diseases and renal pathologies [3]. The main function of FGF23 is the regulation of phosphate levels in the body. It acts on renal proximal tubules by inhibiting phosphate reabsorption and suppresses the formation of the active form of vitamin D. This prevents hyperphosphatemia and excessive calcium absorption. FGF23 can also affect the cardiovascular system and metabolism[4].

Increased levels of FGF23 are observed in patients with CHF. This may be due to a compensatory response to renal dysfunction and phosphate retention. FGF23 interacts with FGFR receptors and Klotho cofactor, activating signalling cascades affecting calcium-phosphate metabolism, oxidative stress and inflammation [5]. High levels of FGF23 are associated with progressive decline in renal function. It promotes fibrosis, inflammation and impaired structural integrity of nephrons. In addition, FGF23 decreases Klotho expression, enhancing renal tissue damage. Activation of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system is also exacerbated by increased FGF23, contributing to nephrotoxic effects. FGF23 physiologically binds to FGF receptors (FGFR) 1/ α -Klotho in the kidney, which leads to decreased levels of sodium-dependent phosphate cotransporters (NaPi2a and NaPi2c), which in turn leads to decreased phosphate reabsorption in the renal tubules and ultimately to decreased serum phosphate levels. In the early stages of CKD, elevated FGF23 levels are combined with unchanged phosphate and parathormone levels. Progression of CKD leads to phosphate retention, which further increases FGF23 levels. At the same time, parathormone levels increase and serum 1,25D concentration decreases, further reducing phosphate absorption. The decrease in 1,25D levels due to increased FGF23 levels is prolonged by inhibition of 1 α -hydroxylase in the kidneys, the enzyme that catalyses the synthesis of 1,25D from the major circulating metabolite 25OHD, and by induction of 24-hydroxylase, the enzyme responsible for the production of 24,25(OH)₂D₃. Thus, decreased intestinal calcium absorption due to reduced levels of 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D combined with low levels of ionised calcium leads to marked increases in parathormone levels and ultimately secondary hyperparathyroidism. [6].

Cardio-renal syndrome is a condition in which cardiac dysfunction causes deterioration of renal function, and vice versa. FGF23 is considered one of the key mediators in this pathological circle linking cardiac and renal failure. It promotes myocardial hypertrophy, fibrosis, and decreased renal filtration capacity [7]. Measurement of serum FGF23 levels may serve as a biomarker of progression of

CHF and CKD. High levels are associated with increased mortality, risk of hospitalisation and decreased renal function. Inclusion of FGF23 in diagnostic algorithms may improve risk stratification in patients with cardio-renal syndrome [8].

Current strategies to influence FGF23 levels include the use of active forms of vitamin D, phosphate-binding drugs, and SGLT2 inhibitors. Some studies have considered the use of monoclonal antibodies against FGF23. However, interference in the regulation of FGF23 requires caution because it plays an important role in maintaining mineral balance [9].

Studies are ongoing to elucidate the causal relationship between FGF23 levels and renal damage in CVD. New therapeutic targets are also being investigated, including the influence of FGF23 on the expression of fibrosis and apoptosis genes, interaction with other hormonal pathways and role in inflammatory processes [10].

Conclusion

FGF23 is an important pathophysiological factor involved in the development of nephropathy in CHF. It not only reflects the degree of mineral abnormalities, but also actively participates in pathological changes at the level of kidneys and heart. Understanding the mechanisms of FGF23 action and the development of methods of its regulation open prospects for improving outcomes in patients with cardio-renal syndrome.

Литература

1. Faul C, Amaral AP, Oskoueï B, et al. FGF23 induces left ventricular hypertrophy. *J Clin Invest.* 2011;121(11):4393–4408.
2. Gutiérrez OM, Mannstadt M, Isakova T, et al. Fibroblast growth factor 23 and mortality among patients undergoing hemodialysis. *N Engl J Med.* 2018;359(6):584–592.
3. Grabner A, Amaral AP, Schramm K, et al. Activation of cardiac fibroblast growth factor receptor 4 causes left ventricular hypertrophy. *Cell Metab.* 2015;22(6):1020–1032.
4. Scialla JJ, Xie H, Rahman M, et al. Fibroblast growth factor-23 and cardiovascular events in CKD. *J Am Soc Nephrol.* 2014;25(2):349–360.
5. Andrukhova O, Slavic S, Zeitz U, et al. FGF23 regulates renal sodium handling and blood pressure. *EMBO Mol Med.* 2014;6(6):744–759.
6. Moe SM, Chen NX. Mechanisms of vascular calcification in chronic kidney disease. *J Am Soc Nephrol.* 2018;19(2):213–216.
7. Isakova T, Wahl P, Vargas GS, et al. Fibroblast growth factor 23 is elevated before parathyroid hormone and phosphate in chronic kidney disease. *Kidney Int.* 2011;79(12):1370–1378.
8. Wolf M. Update on fibroblast growth factor 23 in chronic kidney disease. *Kidney Int.* 2012;82(7):737–747.

9. Ix JH, Katz R, Kestenbaum BR, et al. Fibroblast growth factor-23 and death, heart failure, and cardiovascular events in community-living individuals. *J Am Coll Cardiol.* 2012;60(3):200–207.
10. Seiler S, Heine GH, Fliser D. Clinical relevance of FGF-23 in chronic kidney disease. *Kidney Int Suppl.* 2019;114:S34–S42.